

India's First Brownfield Airport: A Case of Delhi International Airport

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Abstract: The stupendous growth in the civil aviation sector has made it inevitable for India to develop state of the art airports. It has become the need of the hour to develop world class airports in shortest possible time and with the available resources. Public finances alone are insufficient to fund the infrastructure needed to support the tremendous growth in passenger and cargo movements across the nation. There is a need to adopt innovative ways and lure the private players to participate in the growth process through Public Private Partnership (PPP) model. Thus, this study is undertaken to understand the working of PPP model in the aviation sector through the experience of Delhi International Airport Limited (DIAL). DIAL is one among the first airports to be privatized under the Public Private Partnership (PPP) model in India. This study uses descriptive case research method to analyze and highlight the journey of DIAL to be a world class airport catering close to 35% of the total passenger movements in India, and one among the top 30 busiest airports in the world. Further, it discusses the key struggles of DIAL and the lessons learnt from the DIAL experience.

Keywords: Aviation Sector, DIAL, PPP

1. Introduction

India is one among the fastest growing economies in the world. India's growth needs to be backed up by world class infrastructure if it needs to take a leap from a 'developing' to a 'developed' economy. Infrastructure development through public funding has its own limitations. With limited resources at its disposal, the governments always tend to prefer funding such infrastructure projects, like rural infrastructure, where private participation is difficult. Public Private Partnership (PPP) model of funding has emerged as one of the preferred methods for funding infrastructure projects over the years and this model has contributed towards achieving India's dream of creating world class infrastructure. The PPPs have been instrumental in the development of physical infrastructure in India, particularly in the last decade. It has slowly turned out as one of the predominant factors that shoulder the responsibility of making India a hub of world class infrastructure. The growth of PPP model of funding has been rather slow during the pre-liberalization era, which picked up momentum during 1991-2006. Post 2006 era witnessed sharp increase in

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PPP projects across various sectors. Details of evolution of PPP model in India is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Evolution of PPP in India

The government has been constantly addressing factors constraining private investment and implementing appropriate measures to streamline PPP projects. With policymakers keen to involve global firms as well, the future of PPP projects in India looks bright with a band of opportunities for domestic and foreign investors alike. With growing acceptance of the PPP concept in large scale investments, respective governments have formulated specific PPP models addressing the needs of different sectors.

Figure 2: Number of PPP Projects in India

The number of PPP projects currently under development in India across sectors is given in Figure 2. It can be observed that the highest number of projects under development is in the transport sector. The transport infrastructure plays an important role in the development of the country. The transport infrastructure includes roads and bridges, railways, airports, ports, inland waterways, and urban transportation. There lies a tremendous need to develop all these sub sectors under transport. Details of PPP projects in various sub-sectors of transportation, as at the end of financial year 2017, are

summarized in Table 1. It can be observed that roads and bridges occupy the top position, both in terms of number of projects as well as project costs.

Table 1: Details of PPP projects across Sectors

Sectors	Total Number of Projects	Total Project Cost (in INR Crore)
Airports	12	38268.52
Ports (excluding captive)	108	135550.49
Railway track, tunnel, viaducts, bridges	8	6376.08
Roads and bridges	695	462202.25
Urban public transport (except rolling stock)	65	30345.75
Total	888	672743.09

Source: www.ppp.gov.in

2. Aviation Sector- Current Trends

In the past decade, the Indian civil aviation sector has had a glorifying growth. The tremendous growth in the sector has made India the 9th largest civil aviation market in the world and aims to be the third by 2020. The Indian airports today are competing with the best in the world in all respects and this could be attributed to the PPP airports developed in India which includes the Delhi, Mumbai, Bangalore, Hyderabad, and the Kochi airports. The success and the lessons learnt from these airports have aided the government in understanding the PPP model better and have also helped in standardising the entire PPP model in the aviation sector. But for a growing market like India, with the domestic passenger traffic growing at a CAGR of 9.5%, it is not sufficient to have only 5 world class airports. The entry of low-cost carriers led by Air Deccan in 2003 revolutionised the Indian aviation sector. Today the Indian skies are dominated by many low-cost airlines, with Indigo holding the major market share. In 2016, the government initiated a project, UDAN, which is aimed at connecting regional airports across the country. This scheme is expected to increase the demand further. Hence, it is highly essential to come up with better airport infrastructure to cater to the growing demand. The government is not lagging behind and has close to 10 new airports coming up under the PPP model with an estimated outlay of INR 38,268.52 Crore. However, the growth and development of any airport project under PPP is dependent upon the revenue generation ability of the project. A private party would not be interested to invest in an airport if the project is not financially promising. The viability of the airports can be based on the past results and future prediction of the passenger traffic, cargo traffic, air traffic movement and aircraft movements as these are the major sources of aeronautical revenues for an airport. Further, the trends in these areas also help in understanding the capacity enhancements needed, if any, at any of the existing airports.

Out of the five airports in India developed under the PPP model, three (Kochi, Bangalore, and Hyderabad) are greenfield projects, whereas the remaining (Delhi and Mumbai) are brownfield projects. The project costs of these airports are given in Table 2. It can be observed that among the PPP projects, Delhi airport incurred the highest project cost. This paper attempts to make a detailed case study of the Delhi Airport.

Table 2: Project costs of PPP Airports

Airports	Project Cost (INR Crores)
Delhi Airport	12,850
Mumbai Airport	12,500
Hyderabad Airport	2,478
Bangalore Airport	1,930
Cochin Airport	315

Source: www.ppp.gov.in.

3. Review of Literature

The available literature on infrastructure funding through PPP model in India is very limited. Within the available literature, the work on PPP in airports are still less. Summary of selected literature is presented in this section. Pandey, Morris and Raghuram (2010) traced out the genesis of privatization of airports in India from 1998 the time it was first proposed. They highlighted the process of the bidding for both Delhi and Mumbai airports and the challenges in the same. The paper discusses in detail the process and functions of central government, Airports Authority of India (AAI) and the existing Delhi and Mumbai airports authorities in the process of privatization. Mishra and Mohanty (2009) studied the financing and risk management techniques in green field projects under PPP Model with a case study of Rajiv Gandhi International Airport (RGIA) Ltd, Hyderabad and found that in order to counteract the problems associated with various PPP models, several risk mitigation strategies are to be adopted so that both the parties are safeguarded in a better way. Pandey, Morris and Raghuram (2010) discussed the evolution of the draft Operations, Maintenance and Development Agreement (OMDA) from April 2005 when it was first proposed for the bidders, till it was released as a final OMDA in August 2005 after a number of modifications before an extended bidding date. The paper highlighted the critical issues like limits to commercial development of airport land, nature of tariff regulatory regime, contingent liabilities including performance bonds and termination payments, and potential contractual and strategic conflicts along with intra government regulation are discussed and the details of how the final concessional agreement was formed.

From the above review it is evident that there are very few works available in the area and there is hardly any research work after 2010 which uses case study research to put forth the entire process and details of various aspects of PPP airport in India. In the light of this, the current paper attempts to make a detailed case study on DIAL.

4. Methodology

The study uses descriptive case study based research method. Case study research, through reports of past studies, allows the exploration and understanding of complex issues. The case study is limited to Delhi International Airport. The study focuses on the following objectives (aspects) related to the project which are discussion on the funding mechanism, details related to the PPP model adopted, analysis of the operational indicators such as air traffic, passenger, and cargo movements, analysis of the comparative position of DIAL and discussion of key aspects of PPP model and lessons learnt from the projects.

The data required for the study relating to the project details and development of the DIAL is obtained from the official website of the GMR group and the official website of Delhi airport. Further the data related to the concession agreement and the details of PPP are sourced through the official website of Government of India (GoI) on PPP. The details of operational indicators like the passenger traffic, cargo movements and the air traffic movement are sourced through the statistical wing of Directorate of Civil Aviation and the association of private airports in India. Analysis of operational indicators is done for a period of 11 years from 2005-06 to 2015-16. One of the major limitations of the study is the non-availability of relevant data. Apart from the basic structure of financing and the operational indicators, neither the airports nor the AAI provide any relevant information such as the break-up of project costs, various components of costs, the schedule of financing etc. In the light of this, a study of this nature is constrained by whatever data are publicly available. Another limitation is that the number of airport projects completed under PPP model is very few and this coupled with non-availability of data makes it difficult to do a comparative study based on a larger sample.

5. Case Study-Delhi International Airport

Introduction: Delhi International Airport Limited (DIAL) is an airport set up at Palam, New Delhi, in the year 1962 and later re-named as the Indira Gandhi International Airport. Due to increasing growth in the passenger traffic, the existing airport faced tremendous crisis and in the year 2006, the decision was taken to develop the airport under the joint venture between the Government of India (GoI) and the private consortium led by GMR group. The airport is spread around 5106 acres and hosts all prime facilities. It is built under PPP as per the BOT (Build Operate Transfer) model. The period of contract as per the concession agreement is 30 years which could be further extended to another 30 years.

The name of the developer company is DIAL. It is the leading airport in terms of passenger traffic handled in India. It hosts the best of facilities and latest state of the art management systems which includes the Airport Collaborative Decision Making (A-CDM) that assists in keeping take-offs and landings timely and predictable. It is the recipient of the Airport Service Quality (ASQ) Award instituted by Airports Council International (ACI). Delhi Airport was awarded The Best Airport in Central Asia and Best Airport Staff in Central Asia at the Skytrax World Airport Awards 2015.

Brief History: The existing airport at Palam, New Delhi was unable to handle the growing needs of passengers and also the overall growth in passenger and cargo traffic. To meet the growing demand the government considered the proposal of expanding the existing airport and thus the Terminal 3 was proposed to be constructed with state-of-the-art facilities. The government then decided to expand the airport under the PPP model in 2006. In the same year, the Government of India (GoI) signed a Memorandum of Understanding to establish the airport through The BOT model, following which the tenders were called and the private partner was selected using the comparative bidding process.

Capacity: Post expansion, the airport has a capacity of 100 mppa (million passengers per annum) and is currently operating with about 57.70 mppa capacity. This indicates that currently the airport has about 40% unused capacity in terms of handling passengers. But the passenger traffic at the airport has witnessed a compounded annual growth of close to 10% during the last decade. If the same growth rate continues, the airport would be operating at its full capacity in 5 to 6 years from now. Further expansion might require additional capital expenditure.

Funding Mechanism: The funding mechanism followed for DIAL was through PPP, where the state and the central government would hold 26% stake through the AAI and the remaining 74% was given to the private player selected through the bidding process. The consortium was thus created for the remaining 74% stakes consisting of GMR Group (54%), Fraport (a German Transport company) (10%) and Malaysia Airports (10%). However, in the year 2015, Malaysia airports exited the project by selling its stake to GMR group. All the stakes of all the players were put into DIAL to churn the airport project into reality.

Funding of Airport Project: The project cost of the airport project was estimated to be INR 12850 Crore. The entire amount was raised through equity and debt participation. The equity participation was worth INR 3084 Crores which had 26% contribution from the Airports Authority of India (AAI) on behalf of the central government, 10% from the Malaysia airports, 10% from Fraport and the remaining 54% by the GMR group.

PPP Model: The DIAL is built using the Build Operate Transfer (BOT) model of PPP. Under this model, the airport managing company shall enter into an agreement with the government of a country to Build Own and Operate an airport infrastructure for a stipulated number of years (with or without extension) as per the agreement and after the completion of the same, the airport shall be transferred to the government. The DIAL signed the Concession Agreement with the Ministry of Civil Aviation on behalf of the government of India. The agreement highlights the following aspects.

Definitions and Interpretation	Charges
The Concession	Maintenance of Insurance
Grant of Concession	Accounts and Audit
Conditions Precedent	Force Majeure and Termination
Obligations of GoI	Other Provisions
Representations and Warranties	Liability and Indemnity
Construction of The Airport	Dispute Resolution
Operation and Maintenance	Redressal of Public Grievances
Monitoring of Operation and Maintenance	Miscellaneous

The important aspects of the concession agreement under the above heads were:

- 1) The concession agreement is signed for a period of 30 years, from the commencement of the agreement until 30th anniversary of inauguration of airport.
- 2) The same can be further extended to 30 more years at the discretion of DIAL. But the same option can be exercised any day before the 27th anniversary.
- 3) The 30 year period excludes the 37 month construction period.
- 4) Phases are to be planned as per the Master plan of the agreement and the same can be revised every 5 years.
- 5) A total of 4% of the Gross revenue is payable every year to the GoI by the DIAL.
- 6) DIAL has exclusive right to carry out any construction, development, maintenance, and operation at any time.
- 7) There shall be no domestic or international airport in operation within 150 KMS of DIAL before 25th anniversary.

Construction: The construction of the airport project commenced in 2007, and the construction was completed in the record time of 37 months. The terminal was designed by Mott McDonald and HOK (UK). The Engineering, Procurement, and Construction (EPC) contractor was Larsen and Toubro (L and T) limited and Airbiz and Meinhardt Engineering. The Operations and Management contract was with GMR itself. Thus, the work on the terminal building, runway, apron, and the air traffic control tower started in full swing. The airport was inaugurated in 2010.

Financing Structure: The total Project Cost of DIAL was INR 12850 Crores, and the breakup of the funding is as follows:

Table 3: Funding of DIAL

Partners	Cost (INR Crores)	Partners	Cost (INR Crores)
GMR Group	6939	Fraport	1285
AAI	3341	Total	12850
Malaysia Airport	1285		

Source: www.ppp.gov.in.

Figure 1: Funding of DIAL

A project involving huge funding to the tune of INR 12,500 Crores initially, which overshot to INR 12850 Crores, calls for innovative financing methods. Some of the innovative financing methods adopted by GMR group in DIAL include:

- a) Collection of security deposits (refundable) for providing commercial space for development of ancillary services, thus making it a quasi-equity source.
- b) Corporate guarantee for debt backed by the private consortium.
- c) All shares of the participants of the consortium were pledged as security.
- d) The Viability Gap Funding (VGF) in the form of development fee as per the Airport Economic Regulatory Authority (AERA)
- e) AERA guaranteed a fixed return on equity thereby mitigating the operational risk to a certain extent.

6. Analysis of Operational Indicators at DIAL

Passenger Movement: Domestic Passenger movement (DP) and International Passenger movement (IP) in millions at DIAL from 2005-06 to 2015-16 are given in Figure 4. It also

shows the growth rates of domestic (DPG) and international (IPG) passenger movements during the said period.

Figure 2: Passenger Traffic at DIAL

It can be observed that the international passenger movement has shown continuously increasing trend throughout the period. On the other hand, the domestic passenger movement exhibited wide fluctuations in the growth with negative growth in 2008-09 and 2012-13. But it is interesting to note that the entire aviation sector faced negative growth during 2008-09, primarily due to the global recession and high operating costs due to increased fuel costs. Similar trend was witnessed again during 2011-13. But passenger traffic in DIAL showed marked improvements in the following years.

Air Traffic Movement: Figure 5 shows the Air Traffic Movements, both domestic (ATMD) and international (ATMI) during 2005-06 to 2015-16. Air Traffic Movement is measured in terms of number of aircrafts in thousands. The figure also shows the growth rates in both these indicators (ATM DG and ATM IG).

Since the passenger movements and air traffic movement are closely related to each other, the trend in air traffic movement is almost similar to that of passenger movements. The movement of international aircrafts have been growing positively every year with exception of 2014-15 which witnessed a slight negative growth rate. However, the growth in international aircraft movement has been rather slow as compared to domestic aircraft movements, which has shown higher growth rates, albeit, with wide fluctuations. It is interesting to see that the domestic aircraft movements exhibited high growth between 2008-09 and 2011-12 and again during 2014-15 and 2015-16. The low-cost carriers operating in India have contributed in a major way to this growth.

Figure 3: Total ATM at DIAL

Cargo Movement: Cargo movement at DIAL, measured in terms of million tons, are given in Figure 6. The figure gives Domestic (DC) and international (IC) cargo movements along with their growth rates (DCG and ICG). Unlike passenger and aircraft movements, where the domestic figures are greater than the international ones, in case of cargo movements at DIAL, the international figures are greater than the domestic ones. The international cargo handled by DIAL is almost twice that of domestic cargo in most of the years. But the growth rates in both the domestic and international cargo movements have exhibited similar trend throughout the period.

Figure 4: Total Cargo movement at DIAL

A comparison of operational indicators such a passenger and aircraft movements, and handling of cargo during the last decade indicate that there has been substantial increase in all the parameters. Post 2010, when the new airport became fully operational, the growth

rates in all these indicators have shown higher growth rates, except in 2012-13. It can be concluded that, had the expansion project not been taken up, DIAL would not have had enough capacity to handle the increased scale of operations and thus the expansion through PPP model has helped DIAL to scale up its operations. However, looking at the rate at which the operations are growing, the existing infrastructure might be pushed to its full capacity within 5-6 years from now and it is high time the next phase of expansion is taken up.

7. Analysis of the Comparative Position of Dial

Passenger Movement: A comparison of passenger traffic (both domestic and international) at DIAL with that of all other airports in India and the four PPP airports, except DIAL is given in Figure 7. The passenger traffic is measured in terms of millions. The figure also shows the growth rates in all the three indicators. It can be observed that the growth in passenger traffic at DIAL has almost always moved in line with the trend in the overall traffic in the country. DIAL showed the highest growth rate in 2015-16. DIAL accounts for almost 22% of the total passenger traffic in the country and about 38% of all PPP airports put together.

Figure 5: Comparison of Passenger traffic at Delhi with that of All Airports and PPP Airports

Aircraft Movement: Figure 8 shows a comparison of DIAL with all other airports and the other PPP airports in terms of aircraft movement in number of aircrafts in thousands. The aircraft movement in DIAL showed higher growth rates during the initial years of the last decade, however, the same started moving along with the trend of growth in the rest of the country during the later part. DIAL exhibited the highest growth rate again during the last two years. DIAL caters to almost 19% of the aircraft movements in the country and about

36% of aircraft movements among the PPP airports, making it the targets in terms of aircraft movements.

Figure 6: Comparison of ATM at Delhi with that of All Airports and PPP Airports

Cargo Movement: The cargo handling of DIAL with all other airports and the other PPP airports is presented in Figure 9. The cargo handling is measured in terms of millions of tons.

Figure 9: Comparison of Cargo handling at Delhi with that of All Airports and PPP Airports

As far as the growth in cargo handling is concerned, it can be seen that DIAL has shown very high growth rate in comparison to all other airports in the country as well as the other PPP airports. However, the trend in growth rates is seen to be almost similar across all

indicators. Another interesting aspect is that DIAL handles almost 29% of the entire cargo movement in the country and 40% among the PPP airports.

The growth rates seen across passenger traffic, aircraft movements and cargo handling make DIAL one of the fastest growing airports in India. As discussed in the earlier section, sustaining this growth rate would require additional infrastructure and it is high time for the authorities to plan for the same.

8. Key Challenges in PPP in Airports

Approval: The approval procedure for the private player in case of a PPP model is stringent. The lack of single window approval process makes the procedure time consuming and tedious. Further, getting all necessary approvals from different government authorities both state and central adds to the existing woes of the private player.

Delayed Schedules: The process gets delayed multiple times usually due to the incomplete activity on part of any one of the members involved in the project. Constant project delays cause the project costs to rise and delay the completion process. Involvement of government agencies hardly eases out the procedures instead their compliance requirements add to the anguish of the private party involved.

Penalties: The private players are often hesitant to undertake PPP models as there are high project delay and performance penalties which they bear. Since the project is mostly dependent on sovereign functions the private player may at occasions be helpless in fulfilling the project related performance measure and therefore incur penalties for no fault of theirs.

Land Acquisition: This is one of the largest problems that the PPP project faces. Airport projects are huge spread across vast acres of land and obtaining this land is the trickiest aspect for the authorities. The land acquisition in case of brownfield airports is further critical, since for these airports the expansion must happen to the existing airports. Relocating the dwelling around the airport is a herculean task. Even otherwise, that is in case of greenfield airports acquiring thousands of acres of land in a suitable area requires lots of efforts from the government.

Brownfield Development: The development of an existing airport is more challenging than constructing a new Greenfield airport. Along with the problem of land acquisition as discussed earlier there is also a challenge of developing a substandard below quality existing airport into a state-of-the-art airport.

Lack of resources: There is acute shortage of resources like skilled manpower for development of airport infrastructure, maintenance, and operation of the airports. Further,

since the airports are not granted an industrial status making it difficult to obtain debt at a reasonable and desired rate.

9. Lessons Learnt from the DIAL Experience

- a) The cost of development of brown field airports is at an average 3-4 times higher than that of developing green field airports owing to struggles of managing and acquiring the land in and around the existing airport. The design phase also is difficult since the existing design needs to be accommodated and may thus require more time and higher costs.
- b) The private parties are only interested in airports that can ensure high growths in terms of passenger, cargo, and air traffic movements. DIAL that way is one of the largest with almost 25% of the total passenger traffic handled by it. Therefore, it could see private participation even when the anticipated project cost was 3 times the other PPP airport.
- c) Stakeholder management on continuous basis ensuring proper collaboration and flow of work between various stakeholders including the government agencies, airline operators, maintenance contractors etc.
- d) GMR group has been instrumental in developing strategies to ensure timely deliveries of both its project in record time that is 37 months in case of DIAL and 36 months in case of HIAL. The strategy adopted by GMR group is to implement parallel design and construction philosophy for effective time management. Further, they also recruited individuals with prior experience in the area of airport development and provided continuous training in necessary modules to enhance the skill sets of the workers.

10. Factors that Impact the Success of PPP in Civil Aviation

- a) The role of government in ensuring efficient delivery of all sovereign functions at airports like, immigration, customs, clearance etc.
- b) Establish an informed regulatory body with a long-term vision, that would ensure a win-win situation for all involved parties through developing strategies for the same.
- c) To develop effective financing instruments to aid the private player.
- d) The government should further ensure economic IRR to the private player and facilitate the necessary clearance and agreements.
- e) The government should also ensure continuous support to the private players to encourage PPP and consider setting up single window clearance policy and ensure lucrative incentives for the private players.

11. Conclusion

The future of PPP in the aviation sector in India looks bright as the country aims for a higher growth trajectory through strong infrastructure investments. With the increasing involvement of PPP models in development across the sector, the share of PPPs and the private sector in total infrastructure investments is expected to rise. This trend is set to continue over the next decade as well. With the best use of the various lessons learnt from the PPP model adopted in the DIAL case and innovating through new ones, the aviation sector is likely to confront challenges on the path of developing world class airport infrastructure effortlessly.

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